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KNOWLEDGE MAPPING OF CULTURAL IDENTITY PRESERVATION IN AGRITOURISM

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ABSTRACT

Cultural identity in agritourism is being affected by urbanization, commercial tourism and changes in agricultural production. The study approaches knowledge mapping and identifies trends, gaps and future research directions. The data includes 450 standardized articles from Scopus and Web of Science (1995–2025). Bibliometrix and VOSviewer tools are used for keyword co-occurrence analysis, topic mapping and concept evolution. The results show five main keyword clusters: (1) rural tourism, heritage, community; (2) cultural heritage, tourism development, rural spaces; (3) sustainability, planning, local governance; (4) authenticity, destination image, visitor experience; and (5) innovation, growth, context-specific challenges (e.g., intangible cultural heritage, climate). The topic map shows 4 groups, foundational topics (rural tourism, cultural heritage), motivational topics (agritourism, sustainable tourism, local food), niche topics (traditional knowledge, social innovation) and emerging topics (creative tourism, authenticity, identity preservation). The analysis of keyword evolution shows the stability of “cultural identity” and “sustainable tourism”, while also showing the shift from “heritage tourism” to “rural tourism” and the emergence of “intangible cultural heritage” and “community-based tourism”. The study is limited to English data from two international databases, has not been extended to social capital or innovation theory, and has not made specific regional comparisons. The results provide a data foundation for researchers, suggesting policy and practice directions in developing agricultural tourism associated with cultural identity preservation.

KEYWORDS: Cultural Identity, Agritourism, Cultural Heritage, Community-Based Tourism, Rural Development.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the context of many social changes, including the impact of urbanization, commercialization of tourism and changes in production methods, rural cultural identity fades over time (Zhang et al., 2024). When it comes to seasonal cultural activities, like festivals and meals, they are changed to appeal to tourists, but very little of the original is kept (Ma & Lew, 2012); (Stone et al., 2018). However, cultural expressions may become commodified and far from their true origins due to commercial demand (Jv et al., 2024). In this context, agritourism can drive rural development yet raises concerns about identity preservation (Yang, 2012). Without careful attention to authenticity and cultural depth, tourism development may undermine the very values it seeks to protect (Zhu, 2012); (Cohen, 2017).

Previous research on cultural preservation in tourism has mostly focused on historical tourism, cultural tourism, and community-based tourism (Yodsurang et al., 2022). These approaches highlight how cultural values can be maintained through visitor engagement and local participation. On the other hand, cultural identity in agritourism can be considered a hybrid form linked to agriculture and community life that still lacks systematic studies (Kim & Jamal, 2018). Despite considerable study on local cuisine, customs, and rural heritage, there is no knowledge mapping to determine how the area has changed, what issues are developing, and where research shortages exist.

In recent years, the number of academic works dealing with cultural identity in agritourism has increased, leading to fragmentation in terms of topics, approaches and theoretical frames of reference. In that regard, the synthesis of these streams assists in targeting new tendencies, and it offers a comprehensive overview of the field (Klarin, 2024). Instead of relying on personal feelings, the citation data-based approach allows to trace the relationship between concepts, identify key phrases and analyze the level of connection between authors and research schools (Klarin, 2024). This approach, at the same time, clarifies the inherent interdisciplinary nature of the topic, which intersects tourism, rural society and cultural heritage studies.

This study evaluates the structure and expansion of academic knowledge in cultural identity and agritourism literature using bibliometrics, two big databases, and a multi-layered keyword method. By applying tools such as the Bibliometrix R package (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017) and VOSviewer (Van Eck et al., 2010), the study conducts co-occurrence analysis, thematic mapping, and trend tracking to

reveal key themes, knowledge gaps, and future research opportunities.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. *Cultural Identity And Preservation In Tourism*

Cultural identity has been described as a feeling of belonging and sharing within a community in the form of language, rituals, cuisine or folk art forms (Grimson, 2010). This is the core of living cultural heritage, reflecting both collective memory and maintaining the distinctiveness of each community (Buzilă & Lazăr, 2019). The studies of tourism link cultural identity with heritage and community-based tourism, which keeps traditions alive, contributes profit, and promotes culture (Mteti et al., 2025). The important point is that cultural identity is not a static factor, but a dynamic process, adapting to modern contexts while maintaining authenticity.

Otherwise, cultural identity helps the community maintain its traditional lifestyle while exploiting economic opportunities from tourists (Pai et al., 2025). Secondly, it strengthens the ability to transmit knowledge and values to the younger generation (Vázquez-Atochero, 2025). Thirdly, it turns cultural heritage into a driving force for sustainable development, avoiding the risk of tourism destroying local traditions (Lei & Guo, 2025). From this, it can be seen that cultural identity is closely linked to the goal of maintaining cultural sustainability, enhancing social inclusiveness and promoting intercultural dialogue.

In the realm of agritourism, cultural identity becomes greater in significance. Tourism activities associated with agricultural production are not only about visiting farms or experiencing agricultural production, but also about farming practices, culinary processing, or seasonal festivals (Bessiere & Tibere, 2013). In life, it keeps the community connected to the land and the seasons. In culture, it emphasizes cuisine, crafts, and festivals as heritages that are capable of being shared with the visitors (Saeed & Al Atrees, 2025). In society, it strengthens the spirit and community pride of local residents (Izudin et al., 2024). In innovation, applying digital technology and AI brings up new methods to promote identity in agritourism by providing immersive experiences via AR/VR and allowing direct relationships via online platforms (Ranjan & Chaturvedi, 2025).

Thus, cultural identity is a key determinant of authenticity, appeal and sustainability of agritourism. Building a knowledge map in this area will help to illuminate trends and opportunities, and

guide the connection between cultural preservation and agritourism development.

2.2. Agritourism And Cultural Dimensions

Agritourism is widely reported as a bridge between agriculture and tourism, where tourists directly experience activities related to farms and rural life (Phillip et al., 2010). However, the value of agritourism does not stop at agricultural production, but also extends to cultural and social dimensions. Factors such as traditional cuisine, seasonal festivals, farming customs or folk art are cultural layers that create a unique appeal (Szlanyinka, 2016). Therefore, approaching agritourism through the lens of cultural dimensions helps to have a more comprehensive view of its role in preserving and developing cultural identity.

First of all, agritourism helps in reproduction and sustenance of cultural forms of agriculture. Seasonal planting, agricultural processing, and rural festivals provide visitors and communities opportunity to retain practices (Pehin Dato Musa & Chin, 2022). Through transformation of daily activities into tourism products, agritourism not only creates revenue, but also preserves the liveliness of the rural cultural heritage (Che, 2016).

Furthermore, recent studies show that agritourism promotes social cohesion and increases community participation (Kamrul Hassan et al., 2023). When locals directly share their knowledge and stories, interactions with visitors become cultural exchanges, both reinforcing local pride and raising awareness of identity values.

Ultimately, agritourism can also create new channels of local rural culture (Streifeneder et al., 2023). Using narrative, digital media, and virtual reality together may make the experience better and show more people about local culture. In this way, agritourism both preserves tradition and adapts to the development trend of modern tourism (Pehin Dato Musa & Chin, 2022).

When placed within the framework of cultural identity research, agritourism is not only a form of rural tourism but also a bridge between the past, present and future of the community. From there, the knowledge map helps clarify the role of agritourism in preserving and spreading cultural identity in the context of integration and digital transformation.

3. METHOD

3.1. Define Keyword Classes And Set Up Search Syntax

In the process of constructing keywords, the focus

was placed on two main concepts of the study. Cultural identity is mentioned as a category associated with heritage preservation, collective memory and cultural sustainability (Saeed & Al Atrees, 2025); (Izudin et al., 2024). The published documents often use many different variations such as cultural preservation, cultural heritage, cultural conservation, intangible cultural heritage, cultural sustainability, or heritage preservation (Su et al., 2019). Meanwhile, agritourism also comes in a variety of forms including agricultural, farm, rural, farm stay, or village tourism, which illustrates the variety in the titles of the form of tourism (Yuan, 2025).

With these two conceptual axes, the keyword system is partitioned into three layers. The first, layer is concerned with fundamental concepts which take the centre stage. The second layer is a development of variations and synonyms, in order to prevent the omission of significant content. The third level engages such concepts as traditional culture and community-based tourism in order to broaden the problem.

The search approach of the Web of Science (WoW) and Scopus has been customized in accordance with Boolean logic, which is one of the three different kinds of terms (Kuhn et al., 2024), including ("cultural identity" OR "cultural preservation" OR "cultural heritage" OR "cultural conservation" OR "intangible cultural heritage" OR "traditional culture" OR "cultural sustainability" OR "heritage preservation") AND ("agritourism" OR "agricultural tourism" OR "farm tourism" OR "rural tourism" OR "farm stay" OR "village tourism" OR "community-based tourism").

3.2. Data Collection

This research design uses bibliometrix tools for citation analysis and knowledge mapping, so data needs to be collected from reputable international databases. The two sources selected are Scopus and Web of Science Core Collection, which are considered important data repositories in social sciences and humanities research (Donthu et al., 2021). The syntax query process was first used to identify 370 documents in Scopus and 317 documents in Web of Science, and yielded a total of 605 records between 1995-2025 in English.

However, the data from these two sources have differences in structure and metadata format. Therefore, the cleaning steps carried out included removing duplicate records based on title and DOI using the bibliometrix function `mergeDbSources(scopus, wos, remove.duplicated = TRUE)`, standardizing data field names, and unifying

information columns to ensure the ability to analyze (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017). After processing, a total of 135 duplicate documents were eliminated, and 450 standardized documents remained. In this step, data were limited to English publications as recommended when using bibliometrix for cleaning and standardization, to ensure uniformity for subsequent analysis. The latter data ensures wide coverage and uniformity, that is how further Bibliometrix analysis will be built.

3.3. Analytical Techniques

After cleaning the input data set, the study analyzed it using the bibliometrix package in the R environment combined with VOSviewer software. This system analyzes citation data, produces scientific maps, and highlights relationships between research topics (Yuan, 2025).

First, descriptive analysis was conducted to give the overview of the dataset including the analysis of publication trends over the years, the number and the level of author contributions, most cited document, and the distribution by country. Next, keyword co-occurrence analysis was performed using VOSviewer to identify prominent research topics and how they are linked together (van Eck & Waltman, 2014).

In addition, the study applied thematic mapping and cluster analysis to identify topic clusters and their position in the knowledge development process. Finally, evolution analysis was used to track the shift in research trends over time, allowing the identification of established, developing, or emerging topics (Moradi, 2024).

With the approaches of popular methods, the analysis results do not stop at describing data but also establish the structure, trends and orientation of knowledge in the field of cultural identity and agritourism.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Descriptive Information About The Dataset

Research design collects data from WoS and Scopus; the amount of information collected is very large, and the information described in Figure 1 helps identify the overall picture of the research dataset.

Figure 1: The Information Covers Yearly Scientific Output, Top 10 Important Authors, Most Cited Articles, And Country-Level Cooperation.
Source: Author's Visualization, 2025.

Figure 1 illustrates the publication trends over the years, and shows the top 10 authors, documents, and countries with the most contributions, thereby providing a basis for in-depth analysis in the following sections (Jeon et al., 2023). In the years preceding 2010, the publication articles were extremely low ranging between 1 and 6 articles per year. Since 2012, the output started rising and during the period 2016-2019 it had more than 19 articles yearly. Notably, It is important to note that following the Covid-19 pandemic, the articles grew exponentially in 2024, 85 articles were published, and the scholarly community became interested in this topic.

In terms of authors, the top authors with the most cited works, Barbieri C. (273 citations), Jolliffe L. (269) and Macdonald R. (269). These are scholars who have made fundamental contributions to the study of rural culture and tourism (Barbieri, 2013). Other authors such as Zhang T., Chen J. and Hu B. also have over 190 citations, indicating that an international scholarly network has been formed.

At the literature level, the articles by Macdonald R. (2003) with 269 citations and Barbieri C. (2013) with 186 citations are considered classic works. Some recent studies such as Zhang T. (2019) or Gabriel-Campos E. (2021) also have significant citation levels, reflecting the connection between background theory and new approaches (MacDonald & Jolliffe, 2003).

By country, China leads with 97 publications, followed by Italy (30) and Spain (23). Southeast Asian countries such as Malaysia (17) and Indonesia (16) have a presence, while the United States and Portugal have 12 and 10 publications, respectively. This distribution is determined by the contributions of

major research centers in Europe and the development of the developing countries in terms of research on cultural preservation relating to rural tourism (Ruiz-Real et al., 2022).

As these figures 1 demonstrate, the field has never truly expanded until recent decades, and the establishment of international scholarly networks, as well as the continuity between the earlier research and the newest trends.

4.2. Analyze Emerging Keywords

In the context of increasing number of publications, identifying prominent keywords allows to visualize the knowledge structure and development direction of the research field. The keyword map that appears provides a visual view of how topics are connected, as well as the level of academic interest in each content cluster in Figure 2, Table 2 appendix A.

Figure 2: Keyword Co-Occurrence Network On Cultural Identity Preservation In Agritourism
Source: Author's Visualization, 2025.

Figure 2 presents the results of the keyword co-occurrence analysis, showing five prominent topic clusters in the study of cultural identity preservation in agritourism. Each keyword cluster is identified through the frequency of occurrence and total link strength, thereby reflecting the multidimensional knowledge structure of this field.

Cluster 1 (red) reflects the orientation of rural destination development associated with heritage and community participation. Typical keywords include "rural tourism" (199, 565), "agritourism" (31, 97), "heritage" (20, 68), "sustainable tourism" (17, 65), "cultural heritage" (14, 59), "community" (9, 43), "perceptions" (8, 38) and "stakeholders" (6, 33). This structure shows the concern around the organization and management of rural destinations based on

heritage values and community companionship, rather than the focus on "psychological behavior in sustainable agriculture" (Lee & Hsieh, 2016); (Geng et al., 2025).

Connected to this, cluster 2 (green) focuses on the linkage between heritage, tourism development, and rural spaces. Keywords such as "cultural heritage" (103, 417), "tourism" (66, 262), "tourism development" (62, 330), "rural development" (40, 176), "rural areas" (39, 201), "ecotourism" (38, 216), and "heritage tourism" (34, 179) indicate how local identity and destination organization underpin market formation and community benefits (Barbieri, 2013). This cluster complements Cluster 1 by emphasizing community linkage around heritage and destination management as the "glue" connecting agricultural production with tourism experiences (Kastenholz et al., 2018).

Closely related to the above two clusters, cluster 3 (in blue) broadens the perspective to planning and governance for sustainability. Typical keywords include "sustainable development" (76, 315), "sustainability" (42, 210), "rural areas" (30, 120), "rural tourism" (25, 106), "agriculture" (17, 79), and "decision making" (10, 59), reflecting community-based development coordinated through local planning and participation (Situmorang et al., 2019). This cluster reinforces the view that bottom-up participation is an important driver in designing and implementing sustainable strategies (Silva & Leal, 2015).

At the same time, cluster 4 (light yellow) pivots to experience, authenticity, and destination image. The keywords "cultural tourism" (16, 70), "authenticity" (12, 46), "traditional villages" (11, 47), "stakeholders" (10, 49), "destination image" (7, 25), and "community participation" (7, 25) show how stakeholders and local communities co-create culturally grounded experiences that shape tourist behavior and satisfaction, thereby consolidating the attractiveness of rural destinations (Kastenholz et al., 2018); .

Finally, cluster 5 (in purple) points to innovation, growth, and context-specific challenges. With keywords such as "economic development" (9, 55), "innovation" (7, 43), "intangible cultural heritage" (7, 10), "mountain region" (5, 34), "economic growth" (5, 25), and "climate change" (4, 20), this cluster highlights the role of institutional design and innovative approaches in steering rural transformation and in linking agricultural and tourism models (Contini et al., 2009); (Guizzardi et al., 2022).

Overall, rather than social capital, the cross-cutting connector in our map is "cultural heritage",

appearing in Cluster 1 (14, 59), Cluster 2 (103, 417), and Cluster 3 (19, 91). This term links destination practices and rural experiences (Cluster 1), tourism organization and development in rural spaces (Cluster 2), and sustainability-oriented planning and governance (Cluster 3). These connections continue to Cluster 4 through “authenticity” (12, 46) and “destination image” (7, 25), and to Cluster 5 through “intangible cultural heritage” (7, 10) and “innovation” (7, 43), suggesting that preserving cultural identity in agritourism is not only based on material resources but also on the quality of social relations and institutional design that supports change.

4.3. Thematic Mapping And Cluster Analysis

In the process of developing knowledge about agritourism and cultural value conservation, research topics do not hold a fixed position but often change according to theoretical depth and the level of practical connection. Figure 3 and Table 3 illustrate the thematic map, built based on the analysis of key phrases with the level of co-occurrence in four motor themes, reflecting the main development axis; niche themes, representing specialized research directions; basic themes, representing the general knowledge base; and emerging or declining themes belonging to the emerging or less interested group.

Figure 3: Thematic Map Showing Basic, Motor, Niche And Emerging Themes.

Source: Author's Visualization, 2025.

In scientific studies, accurate demarcation of topic clusters is a crucial part in the development of theoretical orientations and development of knowledge bases. The topic map in Figure 3 classifies keywords along two dimensions, with the horizontal axis (centrality) representing the degree of connection to other topics and the vertical axis (density) representing the internal development of each cluster.

First of all, the basic themes group is located in the lower right corner of the map, with high centrality but low density, reflecting the fundamental role, wide connection but not yet exploited deeply.

Notable are “rural tourism” (171, 9679.699), “cultural heritage” (50, 2391.094), along with keywords such as “rural development”, “heritage”, and “cultural identity” (Sun et al., 2011). Although not yet developed in terms of complexity, this group plays the role of a theoretical pillar, laying the foundation for many other topics, especially in the study of heritage, community and rural development (Fusté-Forné, 2022).

Next is the Motor themes cluster, located at the top right, which has both high centrality and density. This cluster has grown strongly and is playing a leading role in the trend. The prominent keywords in this cluster are “agritourism” (138; 8253.725), “sustainable tourism” (73; 3697.324) and “local food” (63; 3593.268). This cluster shows the combination of sustainability theory and local practice, connecting tourism development policy, agriculture and cultural preservation, and creating momentum to promote interdisciplinary research (Barbieri, 2013); (Kastenholz et al., 2018).

Meanwhile, the Niche themes group, located in the upper left corner, has high density but low centrality. Some typical keywords include “traditional knowledge” (19, 1793.326), “social innovation” (15, 1664.385), and “value co-creation”. Although this group has limited connections, it shows theoretical depth and suits studies on social innovation, indigenous knowledge, or community initiatives with potential to evolve independently (Lenao & Saarinen, 2015).

Finally, the Emerging or Declining themes cluster in the lower left corner, with both low centrality and low density. Keywords such as “creative tourism” (20, 1107.436), “cultural sustainability” (22, 1502.857), and “identity preservation” (9, 904.206) indicate that these are new or under-represented themes (Fusté-Forné & Mundet i Cerdan, 2021). However, with the increased interest in creativity and cultural identity, this cluster has the potential to become central themes in the future.

Therefore, the keyword strategy map clearly reflects the multi-layered structure of knowledge in this field. Some keywords such as “cultural identity” from the Basic group and “creative tourism” from the Emerging group can create a bridge between the fundamental topic and the new trend, opening up a potential research direction on the intersection between heritage conservation and innovation in agritourism development.

4.4. Evolution Of Research Trends Over Time

Analyzing the evolution of keywords over time helps to clarify how the theme of cultural identity

preservation has gradually taken shape and developed in the field of agritourism. Detailed results are presented in Table 4 in Appendix A and illustrated in Figure 4, reflecting the movement from the period 1995-2021 to 2022-2025.

Figure 4: Evolutionary Flow Of Keywords In Research Topics

Source: Author's Visualization, 2025.

Figure 4 showed that some of the core themes were maintained whereas others changed or deviated to reflect continuous theoretical and new research perspectives. For instance, terms such as "cultural identity", "cultural sustainability", "development", and "sustainable tourism" maintained an inclusion index = 1.00, indicating a strong thematic persistence across both periods (Silva & Leal, 2015). Interestingly, the term "cultural identity" is translated into "rural tourism" (Occurrences = 3; Stability = 0.04) meaning that the developmental plans of rural tourism continue to rely on cultural preservation (Fusté-Forné & Mundet i Cerdan, 2021).

Meanwhile, the transition pathway of rural tourism is rather diverse, divided into five different themes: "rural tourism" (94; 0.57), "rural development" (15; 0.62), "tourism" (15; 0.58), "cultural sustainability" (3; 0.50), "authenticity" (4; 0.40). This fragmentation lays out a thematic amplification of destination branding to greater cultural and developmental values (Sun et al., 2011); (Guizzardi et al., 2022).

In addition, some themes evolved in naming while preserving their original conceptual core. As an illustration, "village tourism" evolved into "community-based tourism" (2; 0.67), reflecting a more participatory, bottom-up approach to development (Situmorang et al., 2019). In the same way, heritage tourism transformed to rural tourism (6; 0.50), implying the blending of cultural heritage and the variety of destinations (Izudin et al., 2024)

The consistent presence of "intangible cultural heritage" (6; 1.00) together with terms like "rural development" (15; 0.62), "community-based tourism" (2; 0.67), and "authenticity" (4; 0.40) highlights the rising role of intangible cultural values

in agritourism development (Fonseca & Ramos, 2012). These terms not only affirm the role of community identity, indigenous knowledge, and authenticity in tourism experiences, but also reflect the trend of a heritage-based approach and sustainable development (Vázquez-Atochero, 2025).

Furthermore, the flow in Figure 4 shows the academic evolution, from the initial core values to the trend of innovation and interdisciplinary integration. In this context, the cultural identity in agritourism has both maintained stability and expanded into directions such as policy, social innovation and sustainable development, thereby suggesting priority directions for future research.

5. DISCUSSION

In the context of agritourism increasingly being seen as a way to both promote the rural economy and preserve cultural values, the analysis results show that "cultural identity", "cultural heritage" and "rural tourism" have become the central axes in the research. The analysis results are discussed in terms of the connection between key phrases, the position of the topic on the knowledge map and the conceptual shift over time.

Furthermore, the keyword network revealed five thematic clusters reflecting the cross-cutting structure. The cluster on farmers' behavior and sentiment around "perception" and "trust" is consistent with studies that emphasize the role of attitudes in sustainable agricultural development (Lee & Hsieh, 2016). At the same time, the prominence of "social capital" as a bridge between agriculture, community, and policy recalls the view that social cohesion is a decisive factor in rural tourism (Kastenholz et al., 2018). However, the difference is that the current results do not only describe community impacts, but also extend to policy innovation and circular economy, going beyond the traditional approach (Geng et al., 2025).

On the other hand, the thematic map shows a clear stratification of keyword groups, thereby emphasizing the axis of knowledge development. While the Basic themes group such as "rural tourism" and "cultural heritage" play a fundamental role, the Motor themes group with "agritourism", "sustainable tourism" and "local food" reflect the motivation to connect sustainable theory with local practice (Barbieri, 2013). At the same time, the presence of Niche themes such as "traditional knowledge" and "social innovation" shows in-depth but less connected approaches (Lenao & Saarinen, 2015). Furthermore, the cluster of emerging themes such as "creative tourism" and "identity

preservation" reflects the trend of shifting to new topics, associated with creativity and cultural preservation.

In the future, the evolution of keywords suggests noteworthy research directions. One side, the stability of terms such as "cultural identity", "cultural sustainability" or "sustainable tourism" suggests the need to continue to analyze in depth the relationship between conservation and development, instead of considering them as two separate goals (Silva & Leal, 2015). In addition, the shift from "heritage tourism" to "rural tourism" or from "village tourism" to "community-based tourism" confirms the trend of community-based and authenticity approaches (Situmorang et al., 2019). Furthermore, emerging topics such as "intangible cultural heritage" and "authenticity" need to be studied in the context of digital transformation and innovation, in order to link cultural heritage with sustainable development.

However, caution is needed when interpreting the results from the keyword map as some concepts may be used interchangeably, such as "agritourism" and "rural tourism". This overlap may influence how topic clusters are formed, which in turn impacts the identification of research trends.

6. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

Cultural identity occupies a central place in discussions of rural tourism development, both as a foundation for creating the attractiveness of the experience and as an element that needs to be preserved in a changing context. The bibliometric approach allows us to clearly identify how the themes of agriculture, community and heritage are connected, and shows the shift from traditional approaches to new trends. On this basis, the following conclusion summarizes the main findings and draws implications for theory, practice and future research directions.

Furthermore, the analysis results revealed five key phrases, four thematic clusters in the strategy map, and prominent conceptual flows over time. While the foundational themes such as "rural tourism" and "cultural heritage" serve as the general orientation for the study, consistent with previous analyses of rural and heritage tourism (Sun et al., 2011; Fusté-Forné, 2022), the driving themes such as "agritourism" and "sustainable tourism" reflect the close connection between development theory and practice (Barbieri, 2013; Kastenholz et al., 2018). At the same time, the emergence of concepts such as "intangible cultural heritage", "authenticity" and "community-based tourism" shows that knowledge

in this field is expanding and adapting, both inheriting traditional values and accepting global trends (Su et al., 2019); (Yodsurang et al., 2022).

The findings also provide theoretical implications for the research field. Otherwise, the association between "cultural identity", "cultural heritage" and "sustainable tourism" reinforces the view that conservation and development are not two separate directions, but can complement and support each other within the sustainability research framework (Silva & Leal, 2015). In addition, the prominent role of "social capital" as a bridge between households, communities and policies suggests a need to further expand the application of this theoretical framework in agritourism research (Galluzzo, 2022). Furthermore, the emergence of key phrases associated with "innovation" and "circular economy" suggests the direction of combining heritage conservation theory and innovation theory to better explain adaptation in new contexts (Dişli & Ankaralıgil, 2023).

The findings of the study have important implications for a wide range of stakeholders. For government agencies, the results highlight the need to invest in digital infrastructure and enact supportive policies to encourage the use of storytelling and AR/VR in promoting agritourism (Denhere & Shao, 2024). For businesses, the adoption of online platforms and immersive technologies opens up new ways for them to present authentic rural experiences and expand market access (Lin et al., 2024). Finally, for rural communities, proactive engagement in content creation and knowledge sharing will help ensure that digital transformation remains closely linked to local identity and cultural authenticity (Krittayaruangroj et al., 2023).

These results, similar to those of other studies, should be viewed within the current limitations. First, the data were collected only from WoS and Scopus, which may have missed publications outside the international system, suggesting future expansion to local academic sources. Second, the bibliometric approach only sketches an overview, while emerging topics such as "creative tourism", "intangible cultural heritage" or "authenticity" require qualitative research or community surveys to gain a deeper understanding of the context. Finally, the reliance on keyword layers may cause overlaps or confusion between related concepts, such as "agritourism" and "rural tourism," and this should be considered when interpreting the results. These limitations indicate that the findings should be interpreted with caution and point to the need for future studies combining bibliometric data with

qualitative or multi-method approaches.

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Appendix A: Dataset Overview And Tabular Summary

Table 1: Main Information About Data.

No.	Description	Results	Document contents	Results
1	Timespan	1995:2025	Keywords plus (ID)	1038
2	Sources (Journals, Books, etc.)	281	Author's keywords (DE)	1314
3	Documents	450	Authors	1122
4	Annual growth rate %	13.27	Article	322
5	Document average age	5.31	Authors of single-authored docs	86
6	Average citations per doc	11.06	Single-authored docs	90
7	References	20526	Co-authors per Doc	2.98
8	Total duplicate documents	135	International co-authorships %	6.444

Source: Author's analysis, 2025

Table 2: Top Most Frequent Keywords Related To Cultural Identity Preservation And Agritourism.

Cluster	Keyword	Occurrences	Total link strength
1	Rural tourism	199	565
1	Agritourism	31	97
1	Heritage	20	68
1	Sustainable tourism	17	65
1	Cultural heritage	14	59
1	Conservation	13	53
1	Culture	12	32
1	Quality	10	41
1	Community	9	43
1	Areas	8	22
1	Destination	8	31
1	Perceptions	8	38
1	Challenges	7	24
1	Management	7	25
1	Community-based tourism	6	18
1	Food	6	23
1	Stakeholders	6	33
1	Agrotourism	5	22
1	Education	5	21
1	Entrepreneurship	5	20
1	Farm tourism	5	14
1	Rural	5	17
1	Dehesa	4	17
1	Diversification	4	21
1	Evolution	4	19
1	Impact	4	19
1	Impacts	4	16
1	Poverty reduction	4	18
1	Province	4	17
1	Service quality	4	13
2	Cultural heritage	103	417
2	Tourism	66	262
2	Tourism development	62	330
2	Rural development	40	176
2	Rural areas	39	201
2	Ecotourism	38	216
2	Heritage tourism	34	179
2	Cultural identity	18	77
2	Village	14	75
2	Tourism management	13	63
2	Tourism market	13	93
2	Tourist destination	13	85
2	Perception	9	57
2	Tourism economics	8	59
2	GIS	7	37
2	Heritage conservation	7	47
2	Spatiotemporal analysis	7	33
2	Questionnaire survey	6	38
2	Regional development	6	22

2	Rural planning	6	46
2	Cultural landscape	5	25
2	Local participation	5	28
2	Preservation	5	22
2	Traditional knowledge	5	23
2	Cultural sustainability	4	17
2	Land use change	4	24
2	Rural heritage	4	21
2	Strategic approach	4	25
2	Village tourism	4	10
3	Sustainable development	76	315
3	Sustainability	42	210
3	Rural areas	30	120
3	Rural tourisms	25	106
3	Cultural heritage	19	91
3	Agriculture	17	79
3	Rural economy	15	80
3	Rural revitalization	12	44
3	Decision making	10	59
3	Planning	10	49
3	Traditional village	10	43
3	Environmental protection	9	50
3	Tourist attraction	8	44
3	Historic preservation	8	41
3	Tourism industry	8	27
3	Cultural preservation	7	17
3	Development	7	8
3	Marketing	7	38
3	Traditional cultures	7	24
3	Ecology	6	30
3	Regional planning	6	39
3	Big data	5	28
3	Biodiversity	5	21
3	Tourist attractions	5	21
3	Architecture	4	15
3	France	4	22
3	Strategic planning	4	17
4	Cultural tourism	16	70
4	Authenticity	12	46
4	Traditional villages	11	47
4	stakeholders	10	49
4	Landscape	9	30
4	Community participation	7	25
4	Destination image	7	25
4	Model	6	27
4	Rural population	5	25
4	Tourist behavior	5	27
4	Ancient village	4	21
4	Governance	4	16
4	Human	4	13
4	Satisfaction	4	18
4	Tourism potential	4	8
4	Wine tourism	4	17
4	World heritage site	4	20
5	Economic development	9	55
5	Innovation	7	43
5	Intangible cultural heritage	7	10
5	Economic growth	5	25
5	Mountain region	5	34
5	Climate change	4	20

Source: Author's Analysis, 2025.

Table 3: Thematic Map Of Research Themes In Cultural Identity And Agritourism

Keywords	Occurrences	Btw_centrality	Clos_centrality	Pagerank centrality
Rural tourism	171	9679.699	0.002	0.118
Cultural heritage	50	2391.094	0.002	0.039
Tourism	27	2349.168	0.002	0.028
Agritourism	26	1997.308	0.002	0.022
Sustainability	24	1359.988	0.002	0.026
Rural development	23	657.747	0.002	0.017
Rural areas	17	1177.976	0.002	0.015
Heritage	15	573.932	0.002	0.016
Culture	9	257.933	0.002	0.008
Cultural identity	8	437.251	0.002	0.005
Ecotourism	5	435.389	0.002	0.006
Farm tourism	5	298.009	0.001	0.004
Rural	5	393.934	0.002	0.005
Preservation	4	92.587	0.001	0.004
Tourism management	4	319.826	0.002	0.004
Tourism potential	4	142.636	0.002	0.003
Climate change	3	62.369	0.002	0.004
Conservation	3	79.414	0.002	0.003
Farmers	3	180.636	0.002	0.003
Local development	3	52.384	0.001	0.003
Opportunities	3	80.433	0.002	0.005
Place attachment	3	12.492	0.001	0.003
Regional development	3	27.635	0.001	0.003
Tourist product	2	19.34	0.001	0.003
Visitor	3	94.66	0.001	0.004
Agricultural landscape	2	97.188	0.002	0.002
Business model innovation	2	8.96	0.001	0.003
Commodification	2	8.527	0.001	0.002
Depopulation	2	95.583	0.002	0.002
Destination marketing	2	58.955	0.001	0.003
Diversification	2	93.628	0.002	0.002
Economic development	2	12.759	0.002	0.002
Motivations	2	272.566	0.002	0.003
Mountain region	2	333.66	0.002	0.004
Multifunctionality	2	216.128	0.002	0.002
Natural heritage	2	14.654	0.001	0.002
Rural infrastructure	2	25.794	0.001	0.003
Sense of place	2	24.428	0.002	0.003
Tourist perception	2	8.814	0.002	0.001
Tourists	2	159.133	0.002	0.002
Women	2	32.972	0.002	0.002
Village tourism	4	265.969	0.001	0.004
Landscape planning	2	69.253	0.001	0.002
Sustainable rural development	3	7.244	0.001	0.002
Management	2	270.203	0.001	0.003
Sustainable rural tourism	2	82.876	0.001	0.003
Community-based tourism	5	569.745	0.002	0.004
Development	7	337.054	0.002	0.005
Destination	3	222.055	0.001	0.005
Tourist satisfaction	3	191.032	0.002	0.004
Homestay	2	22.151	0.001	0.004
Service quality	2	221.367	0.002	0.003
Landscape	4	350.793	0.002	0.005
Rural landscape	2	7.77	0.002	0.002
Sustainable development	48	4466.002	0.002	0.039
Cultural tourism	16	1238.339	0.002	0.014
Rural revitalization	12	437.769	0.002	0.01
Cultural preservation	7	242.031	0.002	0.006
Community participation	6	229.239	0.002	0.006
Stakeholders	4	41.751	0.001	0.005
Tourism industry	4	165.656	0.002	0.003
Tourism village	3	56.854	0.001	0.003

Digitalization	2	369.685	0.002	0.004
Environmental conservation	2	222.63	0.002	0.003
Influencing factors	2	8.192	0.001	0.002
Infrastructure	2	12.759	0.002	0.002
Land use change	2	199.11	0.001	0.002
Perceptions	2	7.93	0.001	0.003
Tourist	2	148.348	0.002	0.003
Authenticity	9	821.702	0.002	0.01
Quality	5	32.467	0.001	0.006
Destination image	4	546.306	0.002	0.005
Ancient village	2	0.459	0.001	0.002
Agrotourism	5	645.192	0.002	0.006
Education	4	262.773	0.001	0.004
Rural economy	2	336.643	0.002	0.003
Traditional trades	2	1.609	0.001	0.002
Traditional village	10	681.745	0.002	0.005
Tourism development	6	540.485	0.002	0.006
Cooperation	3	77.823	0.002	0.003
Social capital	3	6.076	0.001	0.001
Heritage protection	2	23.066	0.001	0.002
Social exchange theory	2	11.344	0.002	0.002
Intangible cultural heritage	7	290.366	0.002	0.005
Culinary tourism	3	89.847	0.002	0.004
Economic growth	2	2.179	0.001	0.002
Innovative design	2	32.983	0.002	0.003
Rural geography	3	487.032	0.001	0.004
Sustainable tourism	15	2338.284	0.002	0.015
Environment	3	160.211	0.002	0.003
Stakeholder	3	0.333	0.001	0.002
Cultural heritage site	2	95.163	0.002	0.003
Indigenous tourism	2	149.968	0.002	0.002
Traditional villages	9	729.369	0.002	0.007
Rural heritage	4	39.407	0.001	0.004
Creative tourism	3	56.342	0.001	0.003
Sustainable livelihoods	3	83.403	0.002	0.002
Integrated rural tourism	2	94.237	0.002	0.003
Sustainable development goals	2	62.871	0.002	0.002
Tourism resilience	2	57.231	0.002	0.002
Agriculture	7	327.344	0.001	0.01
GIS	3	119.157	0.002	0.004
Tourist experience	3	127.673	0.002	0.005
Tradition	3	57.353	0.002	0.005
Economic impact	2	107.027	0.002	0.003
Geographic information system	2	34.951	0.001	0.003
Resource potential	2	56.735	0.001	0.004
Wine tourism	3	342.207	0.002	0.004
Sustainable	2	73.296	0.001	0.003
Heritage tourism	10	630.92	0.002	0.008
Governance	3	142.615	0.002	0.004
Local food	3	202.927	0.002	0.004
Carpathians	2	136.635	0.002	0.002
Tourism marketing	2	237.181	0.002	0.004
Revitalization	2	24.797	0.001	0.003
Sustainable agritourism	2	14.329	0.001	0.002
Environmental sustainability	2	13.827	0.001	0.002
Agro-tourism	2	146.334	0.001	0.003
Transhumance	2	414.716	0.002	0.003
Cultural sustainability	4	218.528	0.002	0.003
Food tourism	2	275.441	0.002	0.003
Heritage management	2	229	0.001	0.002

Source: Author's analysis, 2025.

Table 4: Keyword Transitions And Thematic Shifts Across Two Research Periods.

From 1995-2021	To 2022-2025	Weighted inclusion index	Inclusion index	Occurrences	Stability index
Agrotourism	Tourism	0.29	0.33	3	0.04
Cultural	Tourism	0.50	0.50	2	0.05
Cultural heritage	Rural tourism	0.50	0.10	27	0.03
Cultural identity	Rural tourism	1.00	1.00	3	0.04
Cultural sustainability	Cultural sustainability	1.00	1.00	2	0.50
Development	Development	1.00	1.00	4	1.00
Education	Tourism	1.00	1.00	2	0.05
Heritage tourism	Rural tourism	0.50	0.50	6	0.04
Intangible cultural heritage	Intangible cultural heritage	1.00	1.00	3	0.20
Landscape	Tourism	1.00	1.00	2	0.05
Rural revitalization	Rural tourism	1.00	1.00	3	0.04
Rural tourism	Authenticity	0.40	0.33	4	0.03
Rural tourism	Cultural sustainability	0.50	0.50	3	0.03
Rural tourism	Rural development	0.62	0.50	15	0.03
Rural tourism	Rural tourism	0.57	0.04	94	0.02
Rural tourism	Tourism	0.58	0.05	15	0.02
Sustainable tourism	Sustainable tourism	1.00	1.00	10	0.14
Tourism industry	Tourism	1.00	1.00	2	0.05
Traditional village	Rural development	1.00	1.00	5	0.50
Village tourism	Community-based tourism	0.67	1.00	2	0.50

Source: Author's Analysis, 2025